

Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper in Water

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Many organic reagents, i.e. 1,5-diphenylcarbohydrazide, oxyldihydrazide, dithiozone, zircon etc. are used for the determination of copper^{1,2}. Of these, 1,5-diphenylcarbohydrazide¹ is widely used but the colour of the complex formed is strongly dependent on the pH of the solution and standing time. Other reagents used are either less sensitive or selective. In the present investigation, *N*-(2,5-dimethylphenyl)-*p*-toluimidoylphenylhydrazine (DMPTIPHZ) is proposed as a new reagent for rapid and selective spectrophotometric determination of copper in water at ppb level. It removes most of the drawbacks of other spectrophotometric methods.

Results and Discussion

DMPTIPHZ instantaneously reacted with Cu^{II} in ethanolic solution to give a brownish green coloured complex having absorption maximum at 410 nm where the reagent blank had negligible absorption. The optimum pH range is 7.0–10.5. At least 10-fold molar excess of reagents was needed for the full colour development of complex and addition of 100-fold excess had no adverse effect. The order of sequence in which reagents were added was not found to be critical. The colour of the complex formed was found stable for at least 20 h at room temperature (22 ± 2°). The temperature of the solution was maintained at 10–27° otherwise the colour of complex faded rapidly. The composition of the complex was determined by mole-ratio, slope-ratio and Job's method of continuous variation. The results indicated the formation of a 1 : 2 (Cu : DMPTIPHZ) complex in the ethanolic solution probably as

The value of molar absorptivity of the complex was found to be $4.00 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 410 nm.

The relative standard deviation of the present method at level of $0.7 \mu\text{g Cu ml}^{-1}$ for 6 replicate measurements was found to be ± 1.0%. The detection limit of the method (causing more absorbance than twice of std. dev.) was $0.05 \mu\text{g Cu ml}^{-1}$. The effect of diverse ions on the determination of $0.7 \mu\text{g Cu ml}^{-1}$ was examined as described in the procedure. The tolerance limit (in ppm) of the ions added are shown in parenthesis : Cl⁻, Br⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, CH₃COO⁻, CO₃²⁻, borate, ammonium, urea, alkali metals (1000); citrate, tartrate (500); F⁻ (400); alkaline earth metals, Zn, Cd, Al, Mn^{II,III}, Cr^{III,VI}, Tl^{III}, Be^{II} (100); Ni, Co, Fe^{II,III}, Ti, V^V, Sb^V, Bi^{III}, U^{VI}, Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, Pb^{II}, Hg^I (50).

Experimental

The standard solution of copper(II) was prepared by dissolving copper foil (E. Merck) (1.0 g) in dilute HNO₃. The oxides of nitrogen were removed by boiling. The dried mass was dissolved in water and diluted to 1 dm³ with double-distilled water. *N*-(2,5-Dimethylphenyl)-*p*-toluimidoylphenylhydrazine (DMPTIPHZ) was synthesised³ by the condensation of equimolar amounts of *N*-(2,5-dimethylphenyl)-*p*-toluimidoyl chloride and phenylhydrazine in ether medium. A 0.1% (w/v) ethanolic solution of DMPTIPHZ was used. A pH 8.0 buffer (0.40 g NaOH and 0.62 g H₃BO₃ dissolved in 100 ml water) and a 1.0% (w/v) sodium tartrate solution were used.

An ECIL GS-5702 spectrophotometer matched with 1-cm quartz cells, a GBC 902-BC AAS with air-acetylene burner, and a Systronic 361 pH meter were employed.

Procedure : To an aliquot containing Cu^{II} upto 15.0 μg were added 0.5, 2, and 1 ml of Na-tartrate (0.5 ml), DMPTIPHZ (2.0 ml) and borate buffer solution (1 ml) and diluted to 10 ml with ethanol (95%, v/v).

The absorbance of the solution was measured at 410 nm against the blank. It followed Beer's law in the range 0.2–1.4 $\mu\text{g Cu ml}^{-1}$ with slope, intercept and correlation coefficient of 0.57, 0.02, and +1.0, respectively.

Application : The application of the present method

TABLE I—ANALYSIS OF Cu IN WATER SAMPLES

Sample	Cu by Present method		Cu by AAS	
	ppb	RSD** ±%	ppb	RSD** ±%
SR ₁	23.2	1.0	24.0	1.5
SP ₁	31.5	1.1	32.8	1.4
SP ₂	29.8	1.2	30.5	1.5
GW ₁	17.6	1.2	18.2	1.6
GW ₂	15.8	1.3	16.3	1.7
GW ₃	16.2	1.2	16.8	1.6

*SR₁ = Kharun river water; SP₁ and SP₂ = Katora and Vivekanand pond water, respectively; GW₁, GW₂ and GW₃ = well-water obtained from different points of Raipur city.

**Relative standard deviation; 6 measurements made.

was tested for analysis of Cu in river, pond and ground water samples of Raipur city and compared with AAS method (Table 1). The water sample (100 ml) was treated with 0.1% (w/v) HCl solution (1.0 ml), then concentrated, diluted to 10 ml and Cu was estimated as above.

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References

1. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd. ed., Interscience, New York, 1959.
2. S. A. BERGER, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1979, 1, 311; P. W. BEAPURE, W. J. HOLLAND, B. ZAK and R. J. THIELKE *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1979, 2, 403; D. NONOV and K. STOYANOV, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1982, 138, 321; F. A. POLOCANDE and J. A. LOPEZLONCIO, *Anal. Quim.*, 1988, 87, 330.
3. K. S. PATEL and R. K. MISHRA, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1985, 73, 91.